

THE ROLE OF PCSK9 INHIBITION IN ACHIEVING XS-LPNP TARGETING INDICATORS IN PATIENTS WITH IBS AND TYPE 2 DIABETES

Muminova Anjela Yuryevna

Abu Ali ibn Sino Bukhara State Medical Institute, Bukhara, Uzbekistan
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20715309>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 11th June 2026

Accepted: 13th June 2026

Online: 15th June 2026

KEYWORDS

ischemic heart disease, type 2 diabetes mellitus, LDL-C, inclisiran, PCSK9, combined hypolipidemic therapy

ABSTRACT

The aim of the study is to evaluate the effectiveness of incorporating inclisiran into combined hypolipidemic therapy to achieve target levels of LDL-C in patients with ischemic heart disease and type 2 diabetes mellitus. The study included patients with very high cardiovascular risk who received double therapy (rosuvastatin and ezetimib) or intensive triple therapy with the addition of inclisiran. It was established that the use of inclisiran ensured a more pronounced decrease in LDL-C by 74.4% compared to 35.7% in double therapy ($p < 0.001$), as well as a higher frequency of achieving the target level of LDL-C < 1.4 mmol/l (85.7% compared to 28.6%). The results obtained confirm the high effectiveness of PCSK9 inhibition in optimizing hypolipidemic therapy and reducing residual cardiovascular risk in patients with combined coronary artery disease and type 2 diabetes.

Introduction. The combination of coronary heart disease (CHD) and type 2 diabetes mellitus (DM2) is associated with a high risk of unfavorable cardiovascular complications due to accelerated progression of atherosclerosis and pronounced lipid metabolism disorders. In this category of patients, atherogenic dyslipidemia is frequently identified, characterized by an increase in the concentration of atherogenic lipoproteins, requiring effective hypolipidemic therapy. Despite the use of high-intensity statins in combination with ezetimib, a significant portion of patients with very high cardiovascular risk do not reach the recommended target levels of low-density lipoprotein (LDL) cholesterol.

In this regard, the application of modern methods for inhibiting the PCSK9 pathway, including inclisiran, which is capable of further reducing LDL-C levels and increasing the effectiveness of lipid-lowering therapy, is of particular interest.

Purpose of the study. To study the effectiveness of incorporating inclisiran into combined hypolipidemic therapy to achieve the recommended levels of LDL-C in patients with very high cardiovascular risk.

Materials and methods. The study included patients with chronic coronary heart disease and type 2 diabetes who received various types of lipid-lowering therapy. The effectiveness of double therapy (rosuvastatin + ezetimib) and the intensive triple regimen with the addition of inclisiran was compared. The main evaluation criteria were the degree of

LDL-C decrease and the frequency of achieving target values according to modern recommendations.

Results. A comparative analysis showed that the inclusion of inclisiran in intensive combined hypolipidemic therapy was accompanied by a more pronounced decrease in LDL-C levels and an increase in the frequency of achieving target lipid indicators in patients with coronary heart disease and type 2 diabetes.

In the group of patients receiving a combination of rosuvastatin and ezetimib, the concentration of LDL-C decreased from 4.2 to 2.7 mmol/L, which was 35.7% of the baseline level ($p < 0.001$). At the same time, the target level of LDL-C below 1.4 mmol/L was achieved in only 28.6% of patients, and a decrease in this indicator by more than 50% was noted in 31.4% of those examined.

In patients receiving triple hypolipidemic therapy with inclusion of inclisiran, a more significant decrease in LDL-C concentration was observed—from 4.3 to 1.1 mmol/L, corresponding to a decrease of 74.4% ($p < 0.001$). Achieving the target level of LDL-C < 1.4 mmol/L was recorded in 85.7% of patients, while a decrease in LDL-C by more than 50% of baseline values was noted in 91.4% of patients.

The obtained data indicate the high effectiveness of PCSK9 inhibition using inclisiran and confirm the advantages of early intensification of hypolipidemic therapy in patients with very high cardiovascular risk.

Conclusion. The results of the conducted study indicate that inhibiting the PCSK9 pathway using inclisiran is an effective modern approach to intensifying hypolipidemic therapy in patients with combined ischemic heart disease and type 2 diabetes mellitus. The inclusion of inclisiran in combined therapy contributes to a more pronounced decrease in LDL-C concentration, a significant increase in the frequency of achieving recommended target lipid indicators, and more effective control of atherogenic dyslipidemia. The use of this therapeutic strategy in patients with very high cardiovascular risk allows for the optimization of lipid metabolism disorders, reduces residual atherogenic risk, and can be considered a promising direction for the prevention of adverse cardiovascular events.

References:

1. Visseren F.L.J., Mach F., Smulders Y.M., et al. 2021 ESC Guidelines on cardiovascular disease prevention in clinical practice. *European Heart Journal*. 2021;42(34):3227–3337.
2. American Diabetes Association Professional Practice Committee. Standards of Care in Diabetes—2026. *Diabetes Care*. 2026;49(Suppl. 1)–S400.
3. Ray K.K., Wright R.S., Kallend D., et al. Two Phase 3 Trials of Inclisiran in Patients with Elevated LDL Cholesterol. *The New England Journal of Medicine*. 2020;382(16):1507–1519.
4. Cannon C.P., Blazing M.A., Giugliano R.P., et al. Ezetimibe Added to Statin Therapy after Acute Coronary Syndromes. *The New England Journal of Medicine*. 2015;372(25):2387–2397.
5. Ference B.A., Ginsberg H.N., Graham I., et al. Low-Density Lipoproteins Cause Atherosclerotic Cardiovascular Disease: Evidence from Genetic, Epidemiologic, and Clinical Studies. *European Heart Journal*. 2017;38(32):2459–2472.
6. Ezhov M.V., Sergienko I.V., Kukharchuk V.V. Modern possibilities of combined lipid-lowering therapy in patients at very high cardiovascular risk. *Atherosclerosis and Dyslipidemias*. 2023.